

The Influence of Example non Example Learning Models for the Result on Theme 3 Subtheme 2 in Grade III SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the influence of the model Example non Example on student learning outcomes Theme 3 Subtheme 2 in k class III SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah , the method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is pre-experimental type one group pretest-posttest. Which will be carried out on October 15 to October 25 2023. 2023, the population in this study is all students of class I II SDN 097805 Rambung Merah with a total of 2 2 students used, namely purposive sampling with two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, and the independent variable (y) in the form of a model Example non Example. Data collection techniques are test techniques with validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differentiating power tests. The results of hypothesis testing using the normality test, homogeneity test, and T-test with the help of the SPSS version 21 program, obtained $t_{count} = 11.287$ with a significant level (2-tailed) 0.000, significant probability <0.05 , $t_{count} > t_{table} = 11.287 > 2.086$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Example Non Example learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 3 class II of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

INTRODUCTION

This increasingly rapid change and development of science needs to be responded to by professional educational performance. This is because education is a very important factor in the development of individuals and society.

Education can be interpreted as a process with certain methods so that people gain knowledge, understanding and ways of behaving in accordance with their needs. Education is also an effort to improve the quality of each individual, either directly or indirectly, who is prepared to support and follow the pace of scientific development and technological progress as well as a means of preparing the nation's children to become quality successors who will advance the nation.

Education is an effort carried out consciously and planned to realize active learning activities, involving students who are active in learning so that students can develop the potential contained within themselves, such as developing religious spirituality, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills. which is beneficial for himself, society and the nation.

According to Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals and the skills needed for education. himself, society and nation.

Based on observations made at SDN 097805 Rambung Merah, researchers found that there were still many students who did not pay attention to the teacher when delivering learning material and were less enthusiastic about participating in the lesson. This can be seen from the model used by teachers when learning takes place in class, namely teachers tend to use monotonous models, such as not taking the initiative to ask about material they don't understand, students just waiting for the teacher to ask before students intend to answer and there are still students who only remain silent when asked a question by the teacher.

The learning used currently is the 2013 curriculum learning or often called thematic learning. The 2013 curriculum is a refinement of the previous curriculum, namely the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP). Learning with the 2013 curriculum requires teachers to be more able to create a pleasant atmosphere and is supported by the assistance of learning media that is appropriate to thematic learning in schools.

In implementing learning, it cannot be denied that every lesson has obstacles in it, especially in thematic subjects. Thematic learning is learning that uses themes by combining several subjects so that it can provide meaningful learning experiences to students.

In solving the problems above, a learning model is needed that can actively involve students in critical thinking, especially in Theme 3 (Objects Around Me) Sub-theme 2 (The Form of Objects) with the content of Indonesian language subject matter, SBdP). Teachers should use learning models that are appropriate and able to make students active, able to think critically, creatively, innovatively and solve problems. For example, learning requires interesting image media, and providing practice questions and student worksheets.

In thematic subjects, the content of the Indonesian Language subject, information was obtained that the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) in this

subject was 70. Based on the results of tests that researchers conducted in class III at SDN 097805 Rambung Merah, there were 8 students whose scores were above the KKM. (passed) and 14 students scored below the KKM (did not pass). This shows that the learning outcomes achieved by students are still low.

**Table 1.1 Class III Indonesian Language Subject Values at SDN 097805
 Rambung Merah**

No.	Mark	Criteria	The number of students	Percentage
1.	≥ 70	Passed	8	38%
2.	≤ 70	Not pass	14	62%
Amount			22	100%

And in the SBdP subject content, information was obtained that the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) for this subject was 70. Based on the results of the test that the researchers conducted in class III at SDN 097805 Rambung Merah, there were 10 students whose scores were above the KKM (passed) and 12 students whose scores are below the KKM (did not pass). This shows that the learning outcomes achieved by students are still low.

Table 1.2 Grade III SBdP Subject Values at SDN 097805 Rambung Merah

No.	Mark	Criteria	The number of students	Percentage
1.	≥ 70	Passed	10	46%
2.	≤ 70	Not pass	12	54%
Amount			22	100%

Based on the problems that occur, the researcher will try to apply the Example Non Example learning model , by using this learning model students can more easily understand the learning material and build their knowledge through the pictures displayed by the teacher. Through this Example Non Example learning model, it is hoped that student learning activities will increase, students will be more active in participating in learning.

This is what prompted the author to conduct research in elementary schools (SD) in order to get a definite picture of "The Influence of the Example Non Example Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes Theme 3 Sub-theme 2 in Class III of SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah"

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Learning is a series of activities carried out by students and teachers with various facilities and materials to achieve predetermined goals. Initial condition of learning outcomes for class III students at SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah. Learning involves more lectures, without giving students the opportunity to practice thinking to solve problems and relate them to empirical experiences in real life so that learning is less meaningful which results in low student learning outcomes. One effort that can influence student learning outcomes is by improving students' problem solving abilities through the Example Non Example learning model . It is hoped that it can influence student learning outcomes.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

The type of research used is quantitative research using experimental methods. According to Sahir (2021:13) Quantitative methods are research with tools for processing data using statistics. Therefore, the data obtained and the results obtained are in the form of numbers. Furthermore, according to Sugiyono (2016: 72), experimental research is a method used to find the effect of certain treatments on others under controlled conditions . The use of this method was carried out based on the research objective, namely to determine the effect of the Example Non Example learning model on student learning outcomes for theme 3 sub theme 2 in class III SDN 097805 Rambung Merah.

Method is research that requires the researcher to manipulate and control one or more independent variables and observe related variables using a systematic method to find a causal relationship between two factors that are deliberately caused by the researcher by eliminating or reducing or setting aside factors. -disturbing factors . The type of research that will be used is an experiment using the " One Group Design Prerest-Posttest" design.

Table 3. 1 One Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Subject	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
Class III SDN 097805 Rambung Merah	Oh ₁	X	O ₂

Description:

O₁ = Pretest value before treatment

X = treatment

O₂ = Posttest value after treatment

Population is the subject of research. If someone wants to research all the elements in the research area, then the research is population research. The study or research is also called population study or census study (Arikunto 2014:173) . Furthermore, according to Sugiyono (2018:117) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics which are applied by researchers to study and then draw conclusions.

Then according to Sujarwedi (2021:21) population is the total number consisting of objects or subjects that have certain characteristics and qualities determined by researchers to be studied later and then conclusions drawn. From the definition above, the population in this study is all students in class I II SDN 097805 Rambung Merah with a total of 22 students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This research was carried out at SD N 097805 Rambung Merah which is located at Jln. Rajamin Purba, Siantar District, Simalungun Regency. On October 15 to October 25 2023. This research was conducted to find out how much influence the Example Non Example Learning Model has on student learning outcomes.

This research is an experimental research with a one group pretest posttest design. Where students are given a pretest and posttest. The pretest is given before using the learning model, the aim is to find out the initial condition of the students before being given treatment. The posttest is given after the learning material is given after using the Example Non Example learning model , the aim is to find out the situation.

1. Validity test

Validity is a measure that shows the levels of validity of an instrument. For validity, use SPSS version 21. The formula used for validation uses Product Moment correlation with a significance level of 5% or 0.05 with $N=22$. Where the test criteria $r_{count} > r_{(table)}$ means valid, or if $r_{count} < r_{(table)}$ means invalid. There are 20 valid questions, while there are 5 invalid questions. Valid questions can be used for the next test.

2. Reliability

Reliability Results Table

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.862	25

Based on the data above, the results of the reliability test using SPSS 21 are already reliable because the coefficient value is more than 0.70 in accordance with the Cronbach's Alpha interpretation above. The reliability test results obtained are included in the reliable category .

3. Test Difficulty Level

Test analysis of the difficulty level of the questions used to test the test questions in terms of difficulty so that it can be obtained which questions fall into the difficult, medium and easy categories. Based on the results of the analysis of the level of difficulty of the 20 questions that have been tested by the researcher, there are 9 easy questions, 4 difficult questions and 7 moderate questions.

4. Differentiating Power Test

The discriminating power of the questions is the ability of the questions to differentiate between groups of students with high and low scores. To see the different power of questions, you can observe the person correlation value in the question validity table. Based on the results of the analysis of the different power tests, 5 questions were obtained from the 20 questions that met sufficient criteria. There were 11 questions that met good criteria. There were 4 questions that received excellent criteria.

Data analysis

Description of Student Learning Results Before Treatment (Pre-Test) . The pretest was given on October 19 2023 in class II of SD N 097805Rambung Merah. The completeness of student learning outcomes is assessed based on the KKM, namely ≥ 70 .

Statistical analysis of data descriptions for class III students' pretest scores can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. 6 Description of Pre-test Learning Results 11th grade students

No	Intervals	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	91-84	-	0%
S2	84-90	-	0%
3	70-83	-	0%
4	<70	22	100%
Total 22			
Complete (≥ 70)		-	0%
Incomplete (< 70)		22	100%
Highest		65	
Lowest		30	
Average		49.31%	

(Source: Research Data)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the lowest pretest score is 30 and the highest score is 65 and the average pretest score is 49.31. All students have scores below the KKM.

Below is a diagram of the results of the pretest scores for class III students at SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah.

Diagram of Pretest Results for Class III Students

The post-test was given on October 23 2023 after being given treatment by applying the Example Non Example learning model to learning theme 3 Objects Around Me Sub-theme 2, Forms of Objects Learning 1. Statistical analysis of data descriptions for class III students' post-test scores can be seen in the table below This:

Table Description of Post-test Learning Results IIth grade students

No	Intervals	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	91-84	2	9.09%
S2	84-90	12	54.54%
3	70-83	8	36.36%
4	<70		100%
Total 22			
Complete (≥ 70)		22	100%
Incomplete (< 70)		-	0%
Highest		95	
Lowest		70	
Average		80.90%	

(Source: Research Data)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the highest score on the post-test is 95, while the lowest score is 70. The average on the post-test is 80.90. There were 22 students who got scores above the KKM. The learning outcomes from the post-test are better than the pretest learning outcomes.

Below is a diagram of the results of the Posttest scores for class III students at SD Negeri 097805 Rambung Merah.

Diagram of Posttest Results for Class III Students

Diagram of Pretest and Posttest Results for Class III Students

Inferential Statistical Data Analysis

1. Normality Test

After carrying out the pretest and posttest from the experimental class, the next step is the normality test which aims to find out whether the data that has been collected has a normal distribution or an abnormal distribution. The normality test used in this research is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test . The decision making data in this test are:

- a. If $sig > 0.05$ then the data is normally distributed.
- b. If $sig < 0.05$ then the data is not normally distributed.

The following is a test for normality of learning result data for class III students at SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

Pre-test and Post-Test Data Normality Test Table

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	Df	Sig.	Statistics	Df	Sig.
Pretestexperiment	0.158	22	0.159	0.944	22	0.242
Posttestexperiment	0.144	22	,200 *	0.917	22	0.067

(Source: SPSS 21 Output)

2. Homogeneity Test

After the data has been tested for normality, the next test that will be carried out is the homogeneity test. This homogeneity test is used to look for samples that come from the same or homogeneous variance. In this study, to test homogeneity, researchers used SPSS 21. The basis for decision making is:

- a. If $\text{sig} > 0.05$ then the data is homogeneous.
- b. If $\text{sig} < 0.05$ then the data is not homogeneous.

Homogeneity Test Table Test of Homogeneity of Variances

Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
1,901	1	42	0.175

(Source: SPSS 21 Output)

Based on the results of the homogeneity test in table 4.10, the significant value can be seen, namely 0.175. This means that the significance is greater than the 0.05 significance level, which means the data is homogeneous.

3. T -test

In this study, a sample test was used to assess the influence of the Example Non Example learning model on learning outcomes in theme 3 class II of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah, which can be seen from the following table:

Table of t-test results

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					T	d f	Sig. (2- tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	setelaheksperiman - sebelum eksperimen	31.59091	13.12816	2.79893	25.77021	37.41161	11.287	21	0.000

(Sumber: Output SPSS 21)

Based on table 4.11 above, it is found that $t = 11.287$ with a significant level (2-tailed) 0.000, significant probability < 0.05 , $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}} = 11.287 > 2.086$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Example Non Example learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 3 class II of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

Discussion

This research was carried out in class II of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah, Simalungun Regency. The 2023/2024 academic year starts from 19 October to 25 October 2023. The population used is all class III students at SD N 097805 Rambung Merah with a sample of 22 class III students.

In this section, the results found in the research that have been carried out will be described. The intended results are conclusions drawn based on the data collected and data analysis that has been carried out. This research aims to determine the effect of the Example Non Example learning model on student outcomes in theme 3 class III of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah, which has 22 students in this study. Before carrying out the research, the researcher first carried out a trial of the instrument at the same level with a different school, namely at SD Negeri 095162 Manak Raya. This trial was carried out in order to determine the number of questions out of 25 questions that would be tested in multiple choice form, namely 20 questions.

Based on the pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 49.31 with all students below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Example Non Example learning model was relatively low.

Furthermore, the average score of the posttest results was 80.90. so after using the learning model students have better student learning outcomes than before using the Example Non Example learning model. After the pretest and posttest normality tests were carried out, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.175 was obtained. Based on the criteria that have been determined, if sig is >0.05 then the data is said to have homogeneous variation. In this case it can be seen that $0.175 > 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the data has the same characteristics or is homogeneous.

After the normality test and homogeneity test have been fulfilled, proceed to hypothesis testing. From the student test results, it was obtained that the t_{count} was 11.287 and the r_{table} was 2.086. Thus, $t_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}} = 11.287 > 2.086$, which means that H_0 is rejected and $H_{a \text{ is}}$ accepted, indicating that there is an influence of the example non example learning model on student learning outcomes with ordinary learning.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the data presented in the previous section, the researcher concluded that the student learning outcomes before being given treatment, all students still had not reached the KKM, namely 22 students (100%) and after being given the treatment, student learning outcomes increased, namely 22 students (100%) has a value above the KKM and is based on the results of hypothesis testing with a significance level of $= 0.05$ and r_{table} of 2.086, t_{count} of 11.287. Thus $t_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}}$ (11.287 > 2.086), it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Example Non Example learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 3 class III at SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

So based on the results of the Hypothesis Test, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is an influence of the Example Non Example learning model on student learning outcomes in theme 3 in class II of SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

Recommendations

After paying attention to the field data in analysis and conclusions, the author provides several suggestions, including:

1. For schools

Schools should pay more attention to student learning outcomes in order to improve the quality of education at SD N 097805 Rambung Merah.

2. For teachers

Teachers should be more selective in choosing to use learning models that emphasize students being more active and enthusiastic about learning

3. For researchers

Researchers are expected to be able to develop the Example Non Example learning model by applying other material to find out whether there is other material suitable for using the Example Non Example learning model .

For future researchers

For future researchers who want to apply the Example Non Example learning model , they can develop and strengthen the Example Non Example learning model , so that the model can spread and teachers are interested in using the Example Non Example learning model .

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